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DETERMINANTS OF WORKING CAPITAL-A STUDY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO INDIAN PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

Working capital plays an important role in any organization. Managing working capital is more difficult than managing fixed capital and the organization is expected to pay utmost attention in terms of working capital so as to ensure tradeoff between profitability and liquidity. In this context this paper has made an attempt to identify the key variables in influencing the profitability of the firm while focusing on working capital decision. The study further evaluates the extent to which profitability of the firm moves in the direction with identified key ratios.

Key words: Liquidity, profitability, tradeoff and Regression.

IMPORTANCE OF WORKING CAPITAL

Working capital management plays a crucial role in the performance of the firm. Since it has the direct relation with firm's profitability and liquidity excessive working capital impairs firms profitability and the inadequate working capital affects the solvency of the firm because its inability to meet its current obligations. So the firm should maintain its working capital at an optimum level.

Net working capital indicates the liquidity position of the firms. And also it suggests that to what extent the working capital needs may be financed through permanent source of funds. It is a conventional rule that the current assets should be twice of current liabilities of a firm. A weak liquidity position makes the company unsafe and unsound. The negative liquidity is harmful for the company's reputation. Excessive liquidity leads to the mismanagement of current assets.

Some important determinants of working capital are nature and size of the business; market and demand conditions. Since the sales depends on factors like inventory turnover ratio; current asset turnover ratio; account receivable days; operating efficiency etc. the firm is expected to give more attention to the above variables so as to sustain the tradeoff between liquidity and profitability.

OBJECTIVES

- To examine the key ratios of working capital for the selected samples.
- To analyze the extent to which profitability is influenced by key working capital ratios.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Along with fixed capital working capital is required to run day to day business activities of a firm. When a business is started, working capital is required to purchase raw materials. The raw materials are then converted into finished goods by incurring some additional cost on it. The sale of goods does not convert into cash immediately because there is invariably some credit sales. During this period, the firm will have to pay wages, cost of raw materials and other expenses required for manufacturing the goods to be sold. To pay all these expenses, working capital is badly needed in the firm. This study finds the impact of the working capital elements on return on total assets (ROTA).

HYPOTHESES

1. H₀: Current ratio does not significantly impact the ROTA of the selected pharmaceutical firms.
2. H₀: Quick ratio does not significantly impact the ROTA of the selected pharmaceutical firms.
3. H₀: Account receivable days do not significantly impact the ROTA of the selected pharmaceutical firms.

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4. H0: Current Asset turnover ratio does not significantly impact the ROTA of the selected pharmaceutical firms.
5. H0: Working Capital turnover ratio does not significantly impact the ROTA of the selected pharmaceutical firms.
6. H0: Inventory turnover ratio does not significantly impact the ROTA of the selected pharmaceutical firms.
7. H0: Current Liabilities to Total Assets does not significantly impact the ROTA of the selected pharmaceutical firms.
8. H0: Natural log on sales does not significantly impact the ROTA of the selected pharmaceutical firms.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

SAMPLE DESIGN

- A sample of ten pharmaceutical companies listed in the Bombay stock exchange was taken for the study.
- The data were collected from the BSE website for the period of 2007-2013.

SAMPLING METHOD

- The samples were chosen based on the judgmental sampling method (non-probability sampling method).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Jisha Joseph has studied the impact of working capital management on firm's profitability and liquidity of Ashok Leyland Ltd, (2014). He had identified that the liquidity and profitability has negative relationship. He used spearman's rank correlation method to identify the relation between liquidity and profitability.

YogeshKumawat had studied the working capital management through ratio analysis with special reference to Rajasthan drugs and pharmaceuticals ltd, (2014). He has taken current ratio, quick ratio, working capital turnover ratio as a measure to analyze the working capital position. In this study he had noticed that the earnings were not utilized properly.

A study on negative working capital and profitability was carried out by Dr. Ashok Kumar Panigrahi (2013). He had identified that there is a positive relationship between working capital and profitability. According to this study the profitability increases with respect to the increase in working capital. He had identified that some companies have higher profitability even though it has negative working capital. It is because of their brand image. But the negative working capital is not desirable in each and every stage of business.

Asha Singh carried out a study on management of working capital (2013). In this study she had identified the concept and importance of working capital; factors influencing working capital; and the relation between the liquidity and profitability.

Dr. A.Vijayakumar et.al, carried out a study on the analysis of size, growth and profitability in Indian two wheeler and three wheeler sector companies, (2013). They have found that the growth of the firm depends on the profitability. They used return on capital employed as an indicator to measure profitability.

A study on Performance of Profitability Management in Lanco Industries Ltd, was done by N.K. Pradeep Kumar and P. Mohan Reddy (2013). They used profitability ratios on sales and investments for the study. The study reveals that the profitability also depends on the company's financial policies.

A.S. Manjulakshmi did a comparative study of profitability of two companies. She had taken current asset turnover ratio, fixed asset turnover ratio, net profit for analyzing the profitability of the company. She had determined that how the growth of the firm was influenced by their ability to earn on its investment.

Nirmal Chakraborty has studied the working capital performance of Dabur India Ltd (2013). He had studied the performance of working capital through the current ratio, quick ratio, absolute liquid ratio, inventory turnover ratio, inventory turnover in days, debtor turnover ratio, account receivables in days, working capital turnover ratio, current asset turnover ratio, etc. With the help of Karl Pearson correlation method he had identified that the relationship between the liquidity and profitability was negative.

Kushalappa S and Rekha Shetty did a study on liquidity, solvency and profitability analysis of selected manufacturing industries (2013). They studied the liquidity, profitability and solvency position of those industries and made a comparison among them. According to the study they have identified FMCG was the most profitable and most solvent industry.

Srinivas Madishetti et al, studied the impact of inventory management on the profitability of small and medium enterprises in Tanzania (2013). They studied the effect of inventory conversion period on gross operating profit of the firms by using regression and correlation analysis. The results show that inventory conversion period has an inverse effect on profitability.

UttamPaulhad studied the role of working capital financing in smooth running of a business (2013). The study reveals the importance of working capital and ways to maintain it. The study proved that working capital can be maintained through the inventories of raw materials, finished products, cash, etc.

Dr. Tej Singh has done a study on inventory and working capital management in the pharmaceutical industry (2012). The study shows the relation between the inventory and working capital management. By using correlation analysis he had found that some companies have positive correlation and some companies have negative correlation between the inventory and working capital management.

RekhaRaheja et al, have studied the impact of working capital on profitability and liquidity (2012). They studied the relationship between working capital and profitability; and impact of working capital elements on profitability of Tata Motors. The study reveals that the working capital elements like asset turnover ratio, working capital turnover ratio are negatively correlated with return on investments.

A comparative study on profitability and liquidity management of FMCG companies was done by Dr. BhaskarBagchi and Dr. BasantaKhamrui (2012). They studied the relationship between the liquidity performance indicators and profitability and also made comparison between the firms. The study proved that the liquidity affects the profitability significantly.

Zohra ZabeenSabunwala has studied the impact of working capital on firm's performance for cement industries (2012). The study shows the effect of working capital elements like account receivables, inventory days, cash conversion cycle and ln sales on return on total assets.

A study on the assessment of liquidity in Indian pharmaceutical industry was done by K. Padmini and C. Svarami Reddy (2012). The study depicts that the current ratio and the liquidity ratio are strongly related with liquidity. Because it helps in the short term solvency.

N. VenkataRamana has done a study on liquidity management of Cuddapah spinning mills Ltd, 2012. Through ratio analysis he studied the liquidity of the company. Using Spearman's rank correlation method he found that the relation between the liquidity and profitability was negative.

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Huma Khan has done a study on the analysis of liquidity, profitability and working capital management of the companies which have been listed in BSE (2012). The study shows that the liquidity has a significant impact on profitability. Dr. Karthikeyan et al, have done a study on the liquidity analysis of the hotel industry in India (2012). They have studied the liquidity position of selected firms by their investments in current assets and short term creditors.

Dr. A. Vijayakumar had done a study on the determinants of profitability (2012). He did the study in the Automobile industry. The study reveals that current ratio, quick ratio, inventory turnover ratio, fixed asset turnover ratio are some of the determinants of profitability.

A study was done on the working capital management and profitability of Andhra Pradesh Power Generation Corporation, by Syed Azhar et al, (2011). With the help of the correlation analysis they have studied the impact of working capital on profitability. The study reveals that working capital turnover ratio, debtor turnover ratio, has high positive correlation with profitability and current ratio, leverage ratio, inventory turnover ratio has negative correlation with profitability.

Ms. RajiniSofat did a study on analysis of liquidity, profitability and risk in cement industry of India (2010). The study was carried out to determine the relationship between the liquidity & profitability and relationship between the profitability & risk. Correlation and t-test are the statistical tools used for the study. The results showed that the liquidity affects the profitability, but every firm has to maintain certain amount of liquidity. The study also shows that the degree of operating leverage affects the profitability adversely.

**Analysis and Interpretation
Regression**

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. Change
1	.829 ^a	.687	.642	6.193	.687	15.123	9	62	.000

Table 1: Shows the linear regression results obtained by analyzing the impact of various independent variables on single dependent ROTA

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5031.865	7	718.838	17.932	.000 ^a
	Residual	2565.602	64	40.088		
	Total	7597.467	71			

a. Predictors: (Constant), ITR, WCTR, CR, LnSales, CATR, CLtoTA, ARdays

b. Dependent Variable: ROTA

Table 2: Shows the F table value for the selected variables.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	6.144	10.049		.611	.543
	CR	-1.455	.850	-.142	-1.711	.092
	ARdays	-.149	.031	-.501	-4.815	.000
	CLtoTA	21.517	8.101	.232	2.656	.010
	CATR	5.232	1.329	.330	3.936	.000
	WCTR	.462	.144	.260	3.207	.002
	LnSales	1.544	.953	.133	1.620	.110
	ITR	.583	.646	.097	.902	.370

a. Dependent Variable: ROTA

Table 3: Shows the significance of each variable on the ROTA.

INFERENCE

Regression test was applied to test the influence of selected liquidity variables on the variable of profitability. Table no (1) shows the model summary of the regression data. The value of R² is about 0.687 indicating 68.7% of variance with respect to dependent variable is explained by the independent variables. Since the model fit is shown through a table of ANOVA (table no 2), the coefficients of all the independent variables are fit enough to run the regression model.

The table no (3) showing coefficients can be interpreted as follows. The influence of Current ratio, Account receivables in days are in negative direction indicating as and when these ratios are maintained at higher level the chance of profitability may come down. The variables like Inventory turnover ratio, Current Liabilities to Total Assets, Current Asset turnover Ratio, Working Capital Turnover Ratio and Ln Sales showed positive sign indicating there is a direct relationship between those variables and profitability. Out of the variables which have a negative influence accounting receivable days has higher impact followed by Current ratio. In the same way the influence of current asset turnover ratio and current liabilities to total assets, Inventory turnover ratio have least influence on profitability. The impact of independent variables on dependent variables is almost significant at 10% LOS.

CONCLUSION

The study shows that the working capital elements like accounts receivable days, current ratio has a significant impact on firm’s profitability. These factors are negatively correlated with the firm’s profitability. The study also reveals that the working capital turnover ratio, current asset turnover ratio, current assets to total assets and sales are positively correlated with the profitability of the firm. Inventory in days and inventory turnover ratio are positively correlated with the profitability of the firm. The study reveals that the liquidity of the firm affects its profitability.

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